

ISic1351

I.Sicily inscription 1351

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

- 1.
2. Ἐνθάδε κείτε Δόξα
3. ζήσασα ἔθη κη
4. τελευτᾷ τῆ̄ πρὸ [---]
5. καλ(ανδῶν) Ὀκτωβ[ρ](ίων)
6. Α,ϸ,ϸ,ϸ,Ο,Α,Τ,Η,Ι,Ι[---]

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation (en)

Here lies Doxa, having lived for 25 years, for her death before the Kalends of October...

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492964

EDCS 39101729

PHI 140853

PHI 316264

Bibliography

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